

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AND DISTANCE LEARNING

Umarova Umida Umarovna – Senior Lecturer
of Mathematical Analysis Department, Bukhara State University
email: umida.umarova.2019@mail.ru

Annotation. *The main approaches of leading domestic and foreign scientists regarding the advantages and disadvantages of using distance learning within the competence-based approach are analyzed.*

Key words: *vocational education, competence approach, distance learning, e-learning, educational technology.*

The competence-activity approach, actively discussed in Russian pedagogical science, replaces the previously existing system of mandatory formation of knowledge, skills and abilities with a set of competencies that will be formed in bachelors based on the updated content of education and in the course of their work. Competence in comparison with the concepts of "knowledge", "skills", "skills" is considered as a more complex social and didactic personal structure. It is expressed in the mobilization of the acquired knowledge, experience, behavioral relations in a particular situation by a person in order to solve various, complex, real professional problems [1, p. 34].

Under the professional competence of a bachelor, we mean the integrative qualities of a specialist, including the level of mastery of knowledge, skills, skills of professional activity based on the formed abilities for self-education, creative activity, operational adaptation in a rapidly changing environment (regulatory framework), as well as the ability to solve problems that go beyond the main type of professional activity [2].

The reality is that the integrated introduction of modern communication systems (integration of mobile telephony, computer networks, satellite and cable

video communications) and virtual reality technologies have brought traditional and distance education to a new qualitative level. Distance learning provides multi-level and flexibility of educational programs, provides a great opportunity in the educational space for the development of cognitive thinking of students.

Today, in higher education institutions in Europe, it is already a traditional practice to use distance learning. The initiator of the use of distance learning in the world was the Open University of Great Britain, which is the leader in distance education in Western Europe. One of the first universities in Germany, which began to actively conduct distance training of specialists, was the Correspondence University of Hagen. Distance learning has also become popular in Spanish universities. The Open University of Madrid (Universidad a Distancia de Madrid) widely uses the following tools in teaching students: Moodle, Gmail, GoogleDocs, GoogleSites, GoogleTalk, Facebook, Twitter, and also created its own three-dimensional virtual space in Second Life. Within the European Union, the leader in the development of software and applications for distance learning is Ireland. Based on the fact that distance learning is an integral part of the Irish national education system, many higher education institutions use elements of e-learning in the educational process [3].

When studying the system of distance education, we will consider the definition of A.A. Andreev, as the most modern and quite fully reflecting the essence of the concept: "Distance education is a system in which the process of distance learning is implemented and the individual achieves and confirms the educational qualification" [4, p. 36].

The competence-based approach, both in distance and traditional education of bachelors, allows not only to introduce new pedagogical technologies into the educational approach, but also to ensure mobility in the formation of the personality of a future specialist under changing labor market conditions, as well as the need for learning throughout life. In turn, traditional methods of teaching legal disciplines should be considered, first of all, from the point of view of those cognitive operations

that students perform in the process of acquiring knowledge of law under the guidance of a teacher. So, for example, N. V. Bordovskaya, A. A. Rean and others distinguish analytic-synthetic and heuristic methods [5, p. 163].

The analytical-synthetic method of teaching in the study of legal disciplines is the main one, since all the cognitive work of students is, first of all, the implementation of analysis and synthesis. When forming legal concepts, students mainly carry out generalizing and abstracting activities. In addition, this method corresponds to the nature of the law itself. The effectiveness of using this method will depend on the ratio in the work of methods of analysis and synthesis, which in turn will depend on the nature of the material being studied, on the stage and task of studying it, as well as on the psychological abilities and capabilities of the trainees. The heuristic method is aimed "at the very essence of cognitive processes, their activation." Revealing the content of the heuristic method, domestic didactics distinguish its varieties: problematic (problem learning), search, or partially search, research [6, p. 95].

The essence of the problematic method of teaching lies in the creation of a problem situation by the teacher, in posing problematic questions to students, in involving students in the process of solving problematic problems, as a result of which students learn the experience of legal activity and form their creative abilities. A problem situation is a situation that generates a task and the need to solve it; students should not only find out what is known and what needs to be found, checked, but also find new, previously unknown ways of solving. The problem situation implies the interest of students, the need for a solution, a creative contribution to the work [7, p. 101].

Search, or partially search, teaching method prepares students for independent research activities. It involves a vision of the problem, the ability to raise a question; find and independently build evidence, justification; draw conclusions from the accumulated facts; make a suggestion (hypothesis); build a plan for testing and confirming the hypothesis; divide a complex problem into a number of smaller,

particular ones and solve them. The teacher only manages the indicated skills. This method provides a high level of mental and professional development of students.

The essence of the research method lies in the active use by the teacher of techniques that ensure the involvement of the students themselves in the observation and accumulation of legal facts, on the basis of which they establish connections between legal phenomena, make generalizations, conclusions, and learn legal patterns.

When implementing this method, various techniques are used (teacher's explanation, work with specific regulatory legal acts, etc.), which in different classifications act as independent teaching methods. The research method is the highest form of manifestation of the cognitive activity of students. When implementing all these varieties of the heuristic method, active and independent activity of students is assumed with the skillful guidance of a teacher who can use various techniques: conversation, demonstration, work with normative legal acts, work with tables, diagrams, etc. V.A. Slastenin, I.F. Isaev, E.N. Shiyanov also distinguished receptive teaching methods. The first method is called explanatory-illustrative. It consists in the fact that the teacher "reports ready-made information by various means, and students perceive, realize and fix this information in memory" [8, p. 273-275].

Special functions, according to the authors of this classification, have the so-called reproductive method, which is designed to form the ability to use the knowledge obtained by the explanatory-illustrative method and to promote the development of relevant private skills and abilities in the subject.

It should be noted that the teaching method is a complex phenomenon, it is possible to distinguish a number of consecutive stages in it. The value of the same method or technique in relation to different tasks of teaching legal disciplines is very different. In modern education of bachelors, it is necessary to use a combination of different teaching methods - analysis of theoretical problems based on normative and scientific sources, compilation of terminological dictionaries, solving cases

(tasks based on real situations), performing practical tasks, etc.[9] It is such an integrated approach that will ultimately contribute to the formation of professional competencies among students, and not only to the assimilation of certain knowledge in the discipline.

The development of the DL system is facilitated by the fact that the traditional forms of conducting classes (a lecture and a seminar where the main theoretical problems of a certain topic are discussed) no longer fully meet the objectives of education in a higher educational institution.

It should be noted that the use of various technologies and models of practice-oriented distance learning in a university is determined in each case by the conditions that the organizations themselves have, namely the presence of:

- the regulatory framework of an educational organization (local regulations governing the procedure and features of the implementation of educational programs using e-learning, distance learning technologies);

- material and technical base (electronic information resources, electronic educational resources, a set of information, telecommunication technologies, relevant technological means and ensuring the development of educational programs by students in full, regardless of the location of students);

- the level of personnel potential of the organization (administrative and teaching staff have the appropriate basic and (or) additional professional education; methodological support for teaching staff using e-learning, distance learning technologies).

Recently, the distance learning system ELearning (e-learning) has gained well-deserved popularity - as a model of education in modern Russian society has already won certain positions. In particular, the evidence of this is the regularly held NOTV conference.

The specifics of the use of eLearning technologies in higher professional education is as follows:

1. Most students are young people under the age of 30 who are active users of computers and the Internet, so they perceive e-learning as friendly;

2. The costs of the university for training can be reduced, since eLearning significantly reduces costs (taking into account the initial investment);

3. The task of the HPE system is to prepare a mobile in the profession and life of a young person, and the use of eLearning increases the amount of human capital of a student, graduate, makes him more competitive, because. information culture is a resource demanded in the labor market;

4. The contradiction of using eLearning in HPE is often the low level of information culture of teachers, and this is a barrier to innovation;

ELearning is a whole set of educational technologies: methods, means of choosing and implementing the educational process from a variety of possible options for its implementation. The totality of new educational technologies can be classified according to a number of grounds. So, they can be represented as a continuum - as more and less loaded with electronic, computer interaction.

REFERENCE

1. Senashenko V.S., Mednikova T.B. Competency approach in higher education: myth and reality // Higher education in Russia. No. 5. 2014. S. 34-46

2. Bondareva O.A. Regulatory framework and methodological support for the formation of professional competencies of a bachelor in the context of the implementation of the Federal State Educational Standard // Uchenye zapiski OGU. Series: Humanities and Social Sciences. 2012. No. 5. URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/normativnopravovaya-baza-i-metodicheskoe-obespechenie-formirovaniya-professionalnyh-kompetentsiy-bakalavra-vusloviyah-realizatsii> (Date of access: 02/10/2016).

3. Korsun G.O. European certificate of e-learning for students of English language faculty in a technical profile / G.O.Korsun // Bulletin of Cherkasy

University. Ser.: Pedagogical sciences. - Zb. articles: - Cherkasy, 2015. - No. 3 (336). - S. 47-50.

4. Andreev A. A., Soldatkin V. I. Distance learning: essence, technology, organization. M.: Publishing House of MESI, 1999. S. 196.

5. Bordovskaya N. V., Rean A. A. Pedagogy: a textbook for universities. St. Petersburg: Piter, 2003. 304 p.

6. Lerner I. Ya. Didactic foundations of teaching methods. Moscow: Pedagogy, 1991. 185 p.

7. Kozlova V.N. Kozlova M.M. Solving educational legal problems as a means of forming professional competencies of law students // Historical, philosophical, political and legal sciences, cultural studies and art history. Questions of theory and practice. Diploma, 2014. No. 4 (42): in 2 parts. Part I. C. 100-107. ISSN 1997-292X.

8. Slastenin V. A., Isaev I. F., Shiyanov E. N. Pedagogy: textbook. allowance for students. higher uch. institutions / ed. V. A. Slastenina. M.: Academy, 2004. 576 p.

9. Ektov A. V. Use of the Case method in the educational process // Concept. 2013. Modern scientific research. Issue 1. ART 53085. URL: <http://e-koncept.ru/2013/53085.htm>. ISSN 2304-120X.